

Characterising living wall microclimate modifications in sheltered urban conditions findings from two monitored case studies

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ABSTRACT: *Green infrastructure enhancements are widely advocated to address heat-related risks in cities. The challenge of implementing enhancements in dense cities has necessitated the development of surface greening, with living walls having gained increased prominence in recent years. This conference paper considered such in-situ applications to quantify the extents of their influence on the microclimates of two sheltered urban conditions. The results highlighted the potency of hygrothermal modifications to be most apparent within the immediate zone, while the disparity between the two studies suggested that with increased shelter the influence is likely to be weaker. Surface temperature monitoring results from the indoor case study presented significant variation. While this was not potent enough to cause radiation asymmetry associated discomfort, thermal sensation and diversity to occupants is probable. These findings highlight the necessity for designers to take account of this proximity influence, and in future designs to increase building occupant access to installations.*

KEYWORDS: *Urban greening, vertical greening, living walls, living wall monitoring, microclimate modification*

1. INTRODUCTION

To address the call for developing passive climate resilience strategies, the research project investigates the influence and effectiveness of utilising vertical greening for reducing the energy loads of urban buildings and bettering their surrounding microclimates. By examining this green infrastructure focus, the project aims to improve urban built environments that would in turn lead to health and wellbeing enhancements of their ever-growing populations.

Although vertical greening includes the two principal approaches of ‘green facades’ and ‘living walls’, recent interest is directed at the latter [1,2]. The plants in such systems root into a substrate (natural or synthetic porous/fibrous media) carrying support-work that includes irrigation and fertigation supply. The greater prominence of living walls is attributed to their flourishing aesthetic appeal, with recent installations introduced to various building typologies, scales, and outdoor, semi-outdoor, and indoor conditions [2–4].

Figure 1. Diagrammatic representation of an installation in an indoor atrium (a); and a semi-outdoor courtyard (b).

The purpose of this conference paper is to present findings from monitoring campaigns carried out at two sheltered living wall (indoor and semi-outdoor) case studies that characterises their microclimate modifications (see Figure 1). The essential parameters monitored included soil, surface, and air temperatures, as well as relative humidity.

Figure 2. Extract from the building section showing the atrium (a); and the living wall in its current state (b).

1.1 Indoor atrium

Within urban buildings the general arrangement often includes a large atrium situated off the entrance. An example of such an atrium is located at a campus building in Cambridge, England (Cfb, Köppen climate), where the northwest atrium surface is host to a flourishing three-storey living wall (see Figure 2).

This installation is 13 m-high and 91 m² in surface coverage, with circa 8,750 evergreen plants from 24 species planted onto a soil substrate based, modular interlocking crate system [5].

Figure 3. Residential courtyard in Primrose Hill, London, basement level court (a); east-facing and south-facing walls of the terrace court (b).

1.2 Semi-outdoor courtyard

The monitored courtyard is in Primrose Hill, London (Cfb), and has living walls installed on three bounding surfaces of the sheltered court, while the remaining north face is represented by the stone and glazed façade of the residential building. The arrangement includes a lower level which continues the living walls at the northwest corner down to form a basement court (see Figure 3). The living walls have an average height of ~4 m and a total area of ~102 m²; with circa 5,000 plants representing 14 species planted onto a soil-based, modular felt-pocket system [5].

2. METHODOLOGY

The monitoring of the indoor atrium case study in Cambridge included the measurement of soil (SoilT), surface (ST), and air temperatures (AT), and relative humidity (RH); while absolute humidity (AH) was calculated. The hygrothermal observations were recorded between June 2018 to March 2019, with the period between June to September 2018 considered as summertime, and between October 2018 to March 2019 considered as wintertime.

The monitoring of the semi-outdoor case study in Primrose Hill included the measurement of AT and RH, with absolute humidity (AH) calculated to characterise the courtyard's microclimate. The hygrothermal observations were recorded between August 2018 to December 2019, with the period between May to September considered as summertime, and between October to April considered as wintertime.

The apparatus used for the exercises included manufacturer calibrated HOBO (Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, MA, USA) and Tinytag (Gemini Data Loggers, Chichester, West Sussex, UK) AT, RH, and ST probes and loggers. All extracted data was processed and analysed using the software MATLAB R2019a (MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA). For large datasets (N > 300), normality was determined with reference to skewness and kurtosis thresholds, with failures assessed with nonparametric tests. Given that

mean value datasets and their relation to probe locations were limited (N < 5), the gathered parameter relationships were plotted as profiles for discussion (see Figure 4 and Figure 5).

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Hygrothermal profiles

Figure 4. Mean AT profiles for indoor case study horizontal (a) and vertical (b) distribution; and semi-outdoor case study horizontal (c) and vertical (d) distribution.

Figure 5. Mean RH and AH profiles for horizontal (a & b) and vertical (c & d) distribution at the indoor study; and for horizontal distribution at the semi-outdoor study (e & f).

3.2 Surface temperatures

Figure 6. Atrium ST and SoilT datasets, with means ('x').

Table 1. Atrium case study ST and SoilT influence.

	SUMMER 2018 & 19		WINTER 2018-19	
Temp. (°C)	ST (L00 - L02)	(ST - SoilT)	ST (L00 - L02)	(ST - SoilT)
Daytime	-0.93 (±0.01), -4.2%	1.95 (±0.01), 8.6%	-1.09 (±0.02), -5.4%	2.48 (±0.02), 11.6%
{L00 ST}	{L02:		{L02:	
{L02 ST}	104.2%}	{L02 SoilT: 91.4%}	105.4%}	{L02 SoilT: 88.4%}
{L02 AT}		{L02 SoilT: 91.9%}		{L02 SoilT: 88.9%}
Night-time	-0.38 (±0.01), -1.8%	0.76 (±0.01), 3.5%	-1.08 (±0.02), -5.4%	2.23 (±0.02), 10.6%
{L00 ST}	{L02:		{L02:	
{L02 ST}	101.8%}	{L02 SoilT: 96.5%}	105.4%}	{L02 SoilT: 89.4%}
{L02 AT}		{L02 SoilT: 97.9%}		{L02 SoilT: 90.7%}

Note: values in '{ }' refer to those relative to L00 and L02 surface temperature (ST); and L02 air temperature (AT) at 100%.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Air temperature influence

With the indoor case study, the *Control* demonstrated weak correlations and shared variance (r^2) with the surrounding outdoor climate. Ambient (*Control*) air temperatures (AT) still varied seasonally, with the summer mean/M = 0.95, ±0.014 K during the daytime, and M = 0.21, ±0.015 K during the night-time warmer than the winter. This modest variation is expected given that the atrium is mostly naturally ventilated. The *Control* reading relationships with atrium probes on the other hand were very strong, and strongest with horizontal than vertical distribution probes. The weakest of these relationships were however during the summer daytime, which suggested interference from another source. Owing to this disruption, living wall horizontal AT distribution influence is best limited to the discussion between the 0.05 m and 1.20 m probes, where the latter datasets showed >99% AT variability with the 0.05 m dataset. When mean AT profiles were examined (see Figure 4a), the summer daytime and night-time, and winter daytime profiles agreed with Pérez-Urrestarazu *et al.* (2016) observations to present increased means at the 1.20 m probe (2.0%, 0.1%, and 0.05%, respectively). Thus, save for the winter night-time profile, all others presented cooler ATs immediate to the living wall (M ~0.5 K coolest AT difference during the summer daytime), in agreement with previous vertical greening studies [1,7,8].

Vertical AT profiles showed the presence of a thermal gradient with means increasing with atrium floor levels L01-to-L03 (Figure 4b). L03 as a result presented the warmest canopy proximate ATs, with the summer presenting the highest means. The gradient confirms the presence of a buoyancy-driven stack-effect, which had pronounced influence in the summer. This flow is also likely to be the principal con-

tributor towards the summertime interference at the *Control* probe mentioned above. The dataset correlations showed that 63% of *L02* and 38% of *L03*'s AT variability to be explained by *L01*. The contributions from rising thermals from the lower level were therefore progressively supplemented by loading from intermediate floor level gains, as well as higher irradiance exposure from the installation upper region's proximity to the atrium rooflight.

With the semi-outdoor case study, the *Control* demonstrated strong correlations and r^2 (98.2%) with the wider outdoor climate. *Control* mean ATs as a result varied seasonally with the summer $M = 7.31$, ± 0.02 K during the daytime, and $M = 6.69$, ± 0.02 K during the night-time warmer than the winter. The much greater mean difference relative to the indoor study is expected given the court's exposure to the elements, regardless of its sheltering boundaries. The *Control* readings however presented lower means for both day and night-time than intermediate horizontal distribution probes (Figure 4c). This suggested interference, which could be attributed to the influence of the building façade's thermal properties. The *Control* AT means however were still higher than the *Canopy* probe, with the latter having presented the lowest means (coolest $M = 0.9$ K influence for the summer daytime, relative to the *Control*). The lowest cooling influence was for the winter night-time ($M = 0.05$ K), which suggested significantly reduced cooling contribution from the evergreen cover. This is expected given that photosynthesis and transpiration is negligible during nocturnal hours, which is exacerbated by evergreen efficiencies being lower in winter [9,10]. Horizontal AT influence distribution was notably nonlinear in the summer, with the intermediate probes (*IPs*) presenting relatively higher means and a daytime drop at *IPO2* (Figure 4c). The reason for this daytime drop is unclear at present, and could be due to mixing introduced from an unidentified source.

Given that only two vertical points were monitored at this study (~3 m elevational difference), a clear thermal disparity was evident with the *Terrace* presenting warmer daytime (1.29 K) and night-time (0.40 K) means relative to the *Basement* in the summer, while in winter this was inverted (1.79 K and 1.96 K, respectively). This latter inverted profile contrasts with the indoor study (Figure 4d), although is explained by the basement court's subterranean environment where it is subject to greater thermal conduction influences from its two retaining boundary walls (including living walls), and heat gains from adjoining basement level living spaces of the residence. Daytime *Terrace* AT variance on the other hand highlighted the significance of irradiance loading variations.

4.2 Moisture influence

With the indoor case study, the recorded *Control* relative humidity (RH) mean range between 43-55% is within the 40-60% range recommended for office environments [11]; although is below the typical requirements (85-95%) to maintain good foliage health

of evergreen plants [1,12]. The *Control* RH readings showed weak shared variance / r^2 (~7%) with the outdoor climate, although seasonal variation was evident with the summer $M = 5.03$, $\pm 0.06\%$ during the daytime, and $M = 6.35$, $\pm 0.06\%$ during the night-time greater than in winter; while absolute humidity (AH) presented summer $M = 15.2\%$ during the daytime, and $M = 13.8\%$ during the night-time greater than in winter. These variations are again expected given that the atrium is predominantly naturally ventilated. Notably, *Control* RH variation was explained mostly by AH variance ($r^2 = 61\%$) than AT variance (17%).

The horizontal RH distribution from the living wall to the *Control* decreased in winter and summer, and both day and night-time, with steeper gradients between the 0.05 m and 1.20 m probes (see Figure 5a). The highest RH was therefore always proximate to the living wall canopy ($M = 5.5\%$, *L02* increase relative to the *Control* for the summer night-time), in agreement with previous vertical greening studies [7,13]. Absolute humidity (AH) profiles complemented this trend, with the maximum summer night-time mean increase for *L02* relative to the *Control* at 13%. The summer daytime difference between 0.05 m and 1.20 m probes however was notably marginal (2.5%), which suggested that during this period the living wall proximate RH increase was mostly affected by AT cooling than by an increase in humidity. This is in agreement with the Susorova *et al.* (2014) study, where a significant fraction of the humidity generated from transpiration was found to be used to maintain foliage in good health during warmer background conditions.

Relative humidity (RH) means at the indoor study also presented a vertical gradient with means decreasing from floor levels *L01*-to-*L03* (Figure 5c). *L01* therefore presented the highest RH ($M = 8.8\%$, for the summer night-time), as well as AH ($M = 14.5\%$, for the summer night-time, relative to the *Control*). The AH mean difference between *L02* and *L03* however was notably minimal (<1%); thereby highlighting the RH reductions at the upper levels to be dominantly influenced by the AT increase of the thermal gradient.

With the semi-outdoor study, the *Control* RH showed strong correlation ($r^2 = 87\%$) with the wider outdoor climate (weaker than AT: 98.2%). The *Control* mean RH as a result varied seasonally, with the summer $M = 10.23$, $\pm 0.09\%$ during the daytime, and $M = 9.40$, $\pm 0.07\%$ during the night-time lesser than in winter; while AH presented the summer $M = 27.4\%$ during the daytime, and $M = 26.6\%$ during the night-time greater than in winter. These larger variations in relation to the indoor study is again expected given the semi-outdoor court's exposure. All RH means were as a result significantly higher (68-97%) than at the indoor atrium study (43-56%), with wintertime means exceeding the upper limit for occupant comfort (70%). AH means however highlighted that humidity was only ~9% greater than at the indoor atrium over the summer, while in the winter it was ~7% lesser. RH variation was therefore explained mostly by AT variance ($r^2 = 18\%$) than AH variance (1.4%).

In agreement with the indoor atrium, the highest RH means for all conditions was at the *Canopy* probe (summer daytime $M = 13.7\%$, highest relative to the *Control*). The horizontal distribution showed RH reduction to be greatest ($M = 18.4\%$ for the summer daytime) between the *Canopy* and *IP01* probe, while at *IP02*, RH showed a relative increase (pronounced for summer profiles, Figure 5e), similar to the mean AT drop discussed earlier. For the summer profiles, examining AH means highlighted this RH increase to be influenced by the drop in AT. In winter however, *IP02* demonstrated an increase in AH to disrupt the linear decay, as observed with summertime AH decay. This again highlighted interference from an unidentified source. Although AH decay in the summer was significant, it still showed substantial influence within the most frequented zone of the 4 m deep terrace court. This is aided by the court's sheltered boundary conditions, where limited exposure to ambient airflow reduces opportunity for humidity advection. Summertime thermal discomfort however is still to be reported by the occupants of the residence.

4.3 Surface temperature influence

Figure 7. Thermogram of the indoor wall showing cooler (blue) substrate areas (5.9 K cooler than the bare wall, left).

With indoor case study surface temperatures (ST), an increase in means was recorded between *L00* (base of the living wall) and *L02* (vertical mid-point), both day and night-time, and in summer and winter (see Figure 6 and Table 1). The relatively weaker correlations presented between the two floor levels in the summer suggested greater thermal contribution from another source to affect the ST increase. This could be partly attributed to the midsection of the installation wall receiving greater summertime irradiance penetration from the atrium rooflight above, relative to the *L00* base condition. The relatively stronger correlations presented with wintertime data (which also presented higher mean STs), on the other hand suggested greater contribution from the AT thermal gradient within the atrium volume, which is further clarified by the marginally stronger correlations ($r_s > 0.97$) between *L02* ATs and corresponding STs.

The recorded *L02* SoilT means were notably lower than the corresponding ST and AT means, both day and night-time, and in summer and winter (Figure 6 and Table 1). This could be attributed to the moisture retention properties (increase in heat capacity) and continued evaporation from exposed soil surfaces. Passive qualitative thermography of the installation confirmed the soil substrate to be the coolest surface within the atrium volume, with some ST differences as large as ~ 6 K (e.g., Figure 7). Significant ST differences between areas could result in radiation asymmetry associated discomfort. The maximum differences recorded however were less than the threshold (>10 K) required to adversely affect comfort, although fell within the range where localised thermal sensation could be reported by proximate occupants [14]. The presence of a living wall could therefore result in occupants experiencing beneficial thermal sensations and diversity [15]; provided their presence is within the immediate zone of influence. The likelihood of the case study building occupants encountering this however is minimal, given that at higher floor levels proximity is restricted by the installation's default arrangement (presence of a void). The beneficial experience of living wall associated thermal diversity is therefore unavailable to this building's occupants.

5. CONCLUSION

Previous studies have presented experimental evidence to suggest significant thermal benefit from exterior vertical greening application. This study presents in-situ monitoring results in relation to an indoor atrium and semi-outdoor court to characterise living wall influence on the microclimates of sheltered conditions. The results highlighted a surface proximate cooling and humidifying influence at the indoor study (maximum air temperature/AT: $M = 0.3$ K and relative humidity/RH: $M = 5.5\%$), and greater influence at the semi-outdoor study (maximum AT: $M = 0.9$ K and RH: $M = 13.7\%$). This disparity in influence suggested that greater the degree of shelter (enclosed system), the weaker the hygrothermal influence is likely to be. This is mostly attributed to the reduced influence of atmospheric advection, where in higher exposure conditions latent and sensible flux advection enhances transpiration associated microclimate influence.

The indoor study results highlighted that most of the humidity generated from transpiration is likely to be re-purposed to maintain good foliage health during the summer. This is particularly significant in indoor conditions where ambient RH is maintained at much lower values than would be required for evergreen plants. In general, the potency of hygrothermal modifications characterised by horizontal distribution was most apparent within the 1-2 m zone from the installation surface. Beyond this range, other phenomena such as the stack flow at the indoor atrium, seemed to cause interference and mixing to disrupt horizontal distribution. Hygrothermal gradation with installation elevational height was also observed at both case

studies, although the semi-outdoor court presented a wintertime inversion explained by its distinct spatial arrangement and resultant thermal exchanges. In general, vertical canopy temperature distribution was significantly influenced by exposure to radiation loading, with remaining contribution from intermediate level thermal sources and sinks.

Although surface temperature (ST) differences were not potent enough to cause radiation asymmetry associated discomfort, they are likely to be potent enough to present thermal sensation and diversity to occupants, which highlights an area that warrants further investigation. The design and siting arrangements of the installation at the indoor case study however precludes such benefits from being experienced by its building occupants at present. This in turn highlights the necessity for designers to take account of the proximity influence and increase building occupant access to installations at future projects.

The monitoring study presented in this conference paper was subject to several limitations. A key limitation of carrying out in-situ monitoring was the inability to place sensors at ideal locations. At the indoor study for example, sensors were suspended across the atrium only where support structures were available. Furthermore, both studies were in occupied buildings, which meant that monitoring schedules had to be modified to not disrupt their day-to-day operation. This was critical at the indoor study, where the building has multiple occupancy and considerable occupant and visitor traffic. Caution must also be raised here in relation to the interpretation of observations. Point-based surface temperature readings for example are not truly representative of the distribution diversity of plant canopies, with quantitative thermography advocated as a better alternative where available.

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